

~~project website~~

*Responsible Research and Innovation approach for transitioning
the traditional industry regions into digitalised industry territories.*

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Project Adviser at European Commission: Cristina Marcone	
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Nature	Report [] Prototype [] Other [Websites, patent filings, etc.]	
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Description of the deliverable (3-5 lines)

This deliverable shows and describes the sections of the first version of the DigiTeRRI project website, which has been published on March 2020. The website, which serves as a critical tool for the external communication of the Consortium with the various audiences, provides general information about the project (e.g., objectives, consortium, methodology), including relevant updates. Interaction and user engagement is measured with Google Analytics, including origin of users and on-site behaviour, among other aspects. A second version of the website is expected to be published soon with a specific site for each territory, displayed in their respective local language; a news section; and the relevant people from each team and an updated contact site.

Key words

Websites, dissemination, territories, partners, online.

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technology, structure and data of the website

Web hosting: Bluehost.com shared hosting service plan
Wordpress version: 5.7.2
Web server: Apache
Database: MySQL version 5.6.41-84.1
PHP version: 7.3.29 (Supports 64bit values)
Server Architecture: Linux 4.19.150-76.ELK.el6.x86_64 x86_64

Outreach SEO

The version 1.0 of the website has not made use of any SEO outreach strategy. Instead, the project has made use of an outreach strategy based on building network with other projects and initiatives through social media and 101 meetings as a way of boosting the ranking of the website. Subsequent versions of the website will include a specific strategy for outreach SEO so the can be exposed to a new audience with the potential of drawing relevant organic and referral traffic to the project site, with a special focus on local stakeholders from the project territories.

The SEO strategy will make use of new links from credible websites that are known as "authority sites" to the targets we want to reach out. These should boost project brand awareness and credibility at the stage where first outcomes of the project will start to be made available.

Web structure V-1.0

our project

DigiTeRRI has been developed to empower three traditional industry regions to harness the opportunities presented by digitalization.

The project contributes to the co-creation of the framework and roadmap for a responsible transition to self-sustaining, digitalized industrial R&I ecosystems. It addresses the challenges in the interplay between business, academia, government and society -the quadruple helix - to guarantee openness, democratic accountability and responsiveness in a process that will in turn promote resilience within these new, digitalized R&I ecosystems.

An RRI approach in key issues such as gender equality, science education, open access, public engagement and ethics during the digitalization process will help to support both organisations and citizens in adapting to the transformation that is revolutionizing industry, the economy and society.

our regions

Territories with traditional industries (steel, automotive, aerospace) will only survive if they learn to adapt to change and create valuable high-tech niche products. DigiTeRRI's mission is to assist policymakers and societal stakeholders in seizing the opportunity to actively promote responsible R&I practices in a new digital economy.

[more info...](#)

our partners

Facts in brief

- **Funding organization**
H2020-SwafS-2019-1
- **Timeframe**
January 2020 – December 2022
- **Funding amount**
2 004 037.50 €
- **Coordinator**
AIT Austrian Institute Of Technology

- AIT Austrian Institute Of Technology GmbH AIT
- Montanuniversität Leoben MUL
- Nordlandsforskning AS NRI
- Wedo Project Intelligence Made Easy SI Wedo
- Materalia MAT
- Zentrum Fur Angewandte Technologie Leoben GmbH ZAT
- The Paper Province Ekonomisk Foerening PP
- Värmlands Läns Landsting Värmland
- Standort Und Marketing Bruck An Der Mur Gesmbh Bruck
- Karlstads Universitet KAU
- Grand E-nov GEN
- Universite De Lorraine UI

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An RRI approach can ensure that the outcomes of the digitalization process align with societal values and needs to satisfy all stakeholders. This involves not only taking economic and research considerations into account, but also addressing social and ecological challenges in accordance with certain ethical principles and normative aims.

The early involvement of stakeholder groups, users and citizens in the process, in addition to the development of additional or alternative knowledge sources, can provide a broader, more plural - and thus more legitimate - basis for decision-making. Furthermore, researchers and industry learn from the needs of users, citizens, and also policy makers.

Project objectives:

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Värmland

The Värmland region is located in west-central Sweden and borders Norway; its proximity to Oslo is a significant factor in the area's business and employment.

The area faces complex social challenges, including slow population growth (with a total of some 274,691 inhabitants, it has only grown by 0.5% since 2009), low education levels, low wages and a lack of employment in comparison to the national average. Much of the population lives in remote rural areas, so companies depend on effective communication networks. The region is home to large tracts of forestland, which are promoted as an asset for the forest industry and local economy.

Värmland's economic activity is concentrated in a few dominant industries: pulp and paper, with approx. 4,000 employees; IT, with 2,000 employees; steel and engineering, with 10,000 employees; and the fastest-growing industry, tourism, with 3,000 employees.

Strategy

The Värmland region firmly embraced the European Commission's Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) in a bid to influence regional and national policies and facilitate participation in other European-driven programmes such as Interreg, ESF, EJFLU, Cosme and Horizon 2020. This is done in conjunction with Europe 2020, the national innovation strategy, the government's research and innovation proposal, the National Strategy for Regional Growth and Attraction 2015-2020 and the local Värmland strategy.

The Värmland Academy for Smart Specialization is a key tool in implementing RIS3 and aims to utilize research for the benefit of industry, County Administration, the Region of Värmland and its municipalities while strengthening the region's research environments.

Significant activities and cluster connections

There are four clusters in Värmland, each with their own organization: steel and engineering (Steel and Engineering), ICT (Compare), forest-based bioeconomy (Paper Province) and the emerging tourism cluster (Visit Värmland).

Innovation platforms and the Innovation Park bring companies and organizations related to research, innovation and SME development together, while the Technical Research Institute of Sweden (SP) has been established in the region.

Research and innovation

While Värmland is described as a "follower" region in terms of innovation, it is still ahead of the EU average in this area.

Gender

The Värmland region applies the RIS3 strategy for gender integration: analytical and mapping procedures have been implemented to raise awareness of the issue throughout the innovation and corporate ecosystem, while studies have been conducted to ensure that gender is prioritized in the development of future policies.

Higher Education

Karlstad University (KAU) offers some 16,000 students access to programmes in humanities, social studies, science, technology, teaching, health care and the Arts at its campuses in Karlstad and Arvika. Its research groups collaborate successfully with H2020 projects and academic partners, while its Grants & Innovation Office also connects researchers with major national and international companies such as Billerud Korsnäs, Stora Enso and Uddeholm, or public bodies such as Region Värmland.

Contact us

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regions

Grand Est

This administrative region in Eastern France spans an area of 57,433 km² and has a population of 5.5 million inhabitants. Bordering Belgium, Luxembourg, Germany and Switzerland, it is a traditional industry area that superseded the former administrative regions of Alsace, Champagne-Ardenne and Lorraine. Industry represents 19.2% of the added value at regional level and includes materials (15% of national production), mechanics, textiles, chemicals and the agri-food sector. Auto giant PSA has three plants in the region.

Strategy

The Grand Est has embraced industrial digitalization and its Regional Council has implemented an ambitious collaborative strategy to support companies in the transition towards Industry 4.0, foster investment (AMI Industry of the future) and strengthen relationships between traditional industries, digitalized industries and RTD performers (AMI numérique). The development and reinforcement of trans-regional cooperation on topics such as AI (European Valley of AI), materials and processes, e-health or energy transition are also a priority for the local authorities, alongside smart specialization strategy (S3).

The Région Grand Est and its Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Grand Est joined efforts in 2018 to create Grand E-nov, the innovation agency that aims to provide services to the region's companies and foster innovation.

Significant activities and cluster connections

Competitiveness clusters were first created in France in 2004 and are formed by companies, research laboratories and training institutions in well-identified areas that focus on specific themes and work alongside national, regional and local authorities. Six are active in Région Grand Est today and are focused on materials and processes (Materialia), health and MedTech (Biovalley France), Construction (Fibres-Energie), water (HYDREOS), mobility (PVF) and bio-resources (IAR). They are based on a triple helix structure that combines enterprises, RTD performers/TTOs and regional stakeholders, and most work on an international level. Grand Est also runs a network of regional clusters focused on textiles (Pôle Textile Alsace) and agri-food (ARIA).

Higher Education

The Région Grand Est educates more than 206,000 students (8.1% of the French student population and 9.2% of French engineering students) at five universities: Strasbourg, Lorraine, Reims-Champagne-Ardenne, Haute-Alsace and Troyes as well as in Engineering Schools. National R&I organizations include INRIA (National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology), CNRS (National Scientific Research Centre), INSERM (National Institute of Health and Medical Research) and CEA (Atomic Energy Commission) through CEA Tech.

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regions

Styria

The federal province (Bundesland) of Styria is located in southern Austria and has a population of 1.2 million inhabitants. Traditionally both a resource-based and industry-oriented territory, it covers 16,401 km² and houses companies in the automotive and electronics industries (semiconductors or electronic components) in the area surrounding the city of Graz.

Upper Styria (referred to as "Obersteiermark") is a mountainous region dominated by iron ore mining and metallurgy. While it has attempted to promote innovation, industry here has remained concentrated on the improvement of steel products technologies. Today, many supplier and customer industries have settled in the area, while the focus on material production has also attracted other activities such as polymer engineering, industrial logistics or environmental engineering.

The economic crisis in 2008/2009 initiated a heavy loss of jobs in the region, which resulted in a decrease in population as younger people flocked to urban areas, a trend that continues today.

Strategy

The local government's economic strategy for the period leading up to 2025 highlights S3 policies that aim to lead the area into the future: technology and creativity, innovation and quality of life, digital transformation, the area as an attractive business location or bridging the gap between strategic planning and making the future a reality. The DigiTeRRI project will further regional policy by including the European Commission's RRI approach and provide an opportunity for trans-territorial learning.

Research and innovation

Styria is considered a robust economic player and an innovative, forward-looking area with the potential to anticipate and adapt to the changes produced by new trends such as digitalization, building on artificial intelligence in production technology. With a research quota of more than 5%, Styria is a leader among Europe's research-oriented regions.

Gender

Today, the number of employees in the Styria region who have successfully completed the Matura exams at the end of their secondary education is lower than the Austrian average and the gender pay gap continues to be an obstacle to gender equality: in Upper Styria, there is clearly a lower employment rate among women than men. In 2017, the general employment rate for women was around 40%, with less than 35% in industrial sectors.

Higher Education

While there are several universities and higher education institutions around Graz in the south, Upper Styria has only two major higher education centres: University of Applied Sciences Upper Austria in Wels and Montanuniversität Leoben, which has some 4,000 students and 1,300 employees.

One of the region's strengths is its strong collaborative network among research, industrial and public organisations. Montanuniversität Leoben and its startup centre have promoted a lively entrepreneurial culture and a new orientation of technology in the area; the collaborations currently underway with schools and other public institutions will serve as an excellent base on which to further develop the activities foreseen in the DigiTeRRI project.

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Marianne Hörleyberger [Scientist]

Marianne Hörleyberger (female) has worked for AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH since 2001. Currently she works mainly for projects with stakeholder engagement such as foresight and road mapping. She started in AIT with analysing data and methodologies such as informatics, scientometrics, and bibliometrics for identification of emerging technologies and the network of agents behind those topics. In some projects, she combines both the analytical methodologies and the qualitative approach. She is currently responsible for stakeholder involvement and stakeholder workshops for in the EU projects IMIRIS (SwaFS-2016-17, GA 788368) and SeeFRI (SwaFS-2018-2020, GA 824588). She has managed and coordinated international and national projects (one was SO-4aIT-Terra, 7.4M EU FP7, 18 partners, and an innovation award). She has also organised several conferences, where she was responsible for the scientific programme. She graduated from the University Vienna and has a PhD in mathematics.

Beatrix Wepner [Scientist]

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Manfred Paier [Scientist]

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Andrea Kasztler [Scientist]

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<https://www.ait.ac.at/en/>

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If you are interested in finding out more about how collaborative strategies and frameworks can support organizations and citizens in the digitalization process, send an email to info@digiterri.eu. We will be happy to answer any questions you may have on our project and partners.

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